

**WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND VARIOUS FEMININE SUCCESS
STORIES (CLASSIC CASE-STUDY PHENOMENA)**

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Abstract:-

“Social Progress can be measured by the social position of the female Sex” – Karl Marx.
As we move towards the next 21st Century and post-covid era in this globalised world, things are changing. Today the feminine- aspects are making sacrifices for the sake of their careers. They are confident and are full of ethical values. They are economically viable and independent. The feminine aspect has had an impact on everything and in all the fields. They are fighting against all the odds and are coming up the hard- way. Their lives are full of struggles and strife, but they are the ones who are taking the risks and are surging ahead in all the potential talents. Women today are an empowered lot and are facing all barriers and are coming up with the flying colours. They have left their footprints everywhere.

Keywords: - Feminine, ethical, values, viable, strife, empowered, footprints.

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Introduction:-

Empowerment means giving or delegation of power or authority. It also means increasing the spiritual, political, social, racial, educational and economic strength of the individuals and the communities. One who is empowered develops confidence in one's own capacities. Women empowerment means the delegation of the authority to the feminine human beings in a very systematic manner. Empowerment of women has improved status in women's education, health and economic opportunities which is the basic need of today's needs and necessities. Women need to be empowered and be made strong in every aspects and thus new avenues comes by, and new challenges arises for building up the family, society and the nation. Pandit

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Jawaharlal Nehru rightly said that the education of a boy is the education of one person, but the education of a women, is the education of the entire family. Women have enjoyed equal status right from the Vedic period. They had equal rights in every aspect be it, socio-cultural and intellectual upliftment in the then society. The success of any strategy in Women empowerment depends on the following factors:-

- 1) Level of Education
- 2) Social Customs,
- 3) Family Planning,
- 4) Health and medical services,
- 5) Clean and Good Environment.

Such an environment should be created for the women that there can be a positive economic and social policies for full development of women to realise their potential and tap it to the fullest. Women should be given equal access to decision- making process and there should not be nay discrimination be made based on the gender – sensitivity.

Review of Literature:-

Women are the layout untapped reservoir of talent in the world (**Hilary Clinton**). **Deswal and Sahni** (2015), states- The only way available to empower the women is to educate them. Education to Women makes them capable to confront distinct life-challenges and improve their life-conditions. You educate a man, you educate a human; you educate a woman, you educate a generation (**Brigham Young**). So we see a human (feminine aspects) should be given a free-hand in all their potency of talents showing.

Objectives:-

- 1) To build up the confidence of the women through the success empowered stories
- 2) To bring about a social change through the reading of the empowered women success stories.
- 3) To build up the socio- economic status in the women’s life through the empowered women success stories.

Importance of the study :-

- 1) The success stories of the empowered women can be taken as the basis for implementing those success - strategies in one’s life.

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2) There may be a great impact on the moral, ethical values and the social aspects of the women through these empowered women stories.

Hypothesis of the study :-

The success- stories of the empowered women can really tap the potential of the other women, when thoroughly followed by the book-rules.

Methodology:-

The methodology is based on the Case- study Method and various Phenomenological aspects. This research paper are based on the secondary data, which is taken through various books, articles , journals, magazines, newspapers, pamphlets, paper- clips and different types of collections.

Data- analysis :-

Some of the Case- studies are taken with respect to prove that the Empowered women can really make a difference in one's lives as well as the other people lives.

- **Sudha Murthy** is an Indian engineering teacher. Murthy began her professional career as computer science engineer. She became the first female engineer hired in India's largest auto manufacturer company TATA Engineering and Locomotive Company (TELCO) .Murthy joined the company as a Development Engineer in Pune, then moved to Mumbai and Jamshedpur. She is the chairperson of the Infosys Foundation and a member of Public Health Care initiative of the Gates Foundation. She has founded several orphanages, participated in rural development efforts, and has supported the Karnataka Government schools with Computer and Library facilities. She has established the "The Murthy Classical Library of India" at Harvard University. She has got the "Best Teacher" award in 1995 from Rotary Club at Bangalore. She has also appeared in Kaun Banega Crorepati , season 11 in its Karamveer episode of finale work. She is the trustee members of the Murthy's Infosys Foundation, a public charitable trust founded in 1996. This foundation has built 2,300 houses in flood- effected areas. Her social work covers the healthcare, education, empowerment of women, public hygiene, art and culture, and also poverty alleviation measures at the grassroot levels. Her vision with the school has resulted in 70,000 libraries in the country. The Government of Karnataka has awarded her prestigious

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award - “ Attimabbe Award” for her literary work in 2011-12. This is the **social- work** perspective of the empowered women.

- **Ms. Sunidhi Chauhan** is an Indian playback singer who has the credit of singing more than 2000 songs. She began to sing at the age of four. She was also the member lead- singer in Kalyanji’s “little wonders” troupe. Chauhan in the meantime decided to do different things as the years passed by. She has firm belief in the Divine Providence. She quotes that – God has always being her inner conscience and her intuition, her inner self, and her guiding force and her angel, who protects her. She further says- She always had a firm deep faith in the supreme divine power and has never wavered from it, she believes that God gives everyone an opportunity to grow in every arena of life. This is the **music** perspective empowered women.
- **Ms. Pratibha Patil** – was the 12 th current President of the Republic of India and the first women to hold the office. She had won the presidential election after defeating the nearest rival – Mr. Bhairon Singh Shekhawat. Together with her husband, she has set up an educational institute, Vidya Bharathi Shikshan Prasarak Mandal, which runs a chain of schools and colleges in Jalgaon and Mumbai. This is the classic example of **Political** empowered Women.
- **Indira Krishanmurthy Nooyi** was the Chairperson and the CEO of Pepsico incorporated. She also was the successor fellow of the Yale Corporation. She was the Class B director of the Board of Directors of the New York Federal Reserve. She served as a member of the Foundation of the World Economic Forum, International Rescue Committee. She also was the member of the Board of Trustees of Eisenhower Fellowships, and the list continues on and on. This is the **corporate** example of Empowered women.
- **P.T. Usha** , an Indian athlete has been associated with the Indian racing track since 1979. She hails from Keral and is called as the Queen of the Indian track and field. She is one of the greatest athletes India has ever produced. In Kerala, she is also named as the – Payyoli Express. This is the **sports –physical** aspect of the empowered women.
- **Rani Lakshuibai**, was originally named as – Manikarnika at birth. She was born in the Maharashtra karhade Brahmin family. After Marriage, she was given the name as the – Lakshuibai. Rani Lakshuibai was a national heroine and was epitome in the feminine aspects.

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It is said that Colonel Malleson – quoted - ... her countrymen will always believe that she was driven by ill- treatment into rebellion that her cause was a righteous cause. To them, she always will be a Heroine... This is the **soldier** aspect of the empowered women, brave and ferocious.

Thus the above success stories of the empowered women will lead other women to newer paradigm shifts of lives and channelize their glories to more heights.

Suggestions for future research :-

- There will be a greater diversity of Women empowerment through the success stories given in these stories.
- More facet of talent-potential can be made known through this paper.
- This paper has a wide range of proving feminist talent potencies and can lead to many other pathways.

Gaps :-

- The women are still discriminated along the male – gender sensitivity.
- The women are still harassed and abused, when trying to reach at the top.
- The women at certain places and creed are not educated, because of certain ideologies.
- The women are still try to be put down and suppressed, when they try to come up

Conclusions :-

- The total empowerment of the women and the socio-economic status should be taken utmost care and necessities.
- Women should be taught new e- learning resources, to tap others talents.
- Everyone should be given a raw deal irrespective of the gender aspects.
- If a feminine aspect has to shine, even the nature with all its positivity backs that aspects and makes it to reach at the top most pedestal.

So, finally, a Holistic approach should be taken to empower women and see that everybody grow with hands- in-hands together and make the world a better place to live, with our hearts, mind and soul pure, taking every human beings to new dimension of living. It is said, that – “The hand that rocks the cradle rules the world”, so empower women and be empowered in your lives in what ever aspects it may be. The crux finale is - “**Ab Nari mukthi ka Zamana Nahin Hain, Nari chetna aur Nari Shakthi ka Zamana hain**”.

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